

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report for

TEBT-2024-0011

Submission information table

Submission Title	An Environmental Health Vocabulary and its Semi-Automated Curation Workflow
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0011
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	Round 1: 2 plus comments from editor Round 2: 1 re-review plus comments from editor Round 3: Editor's final decision
Submission Type	Methodology ▾
Preprint DOI	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11176258
Evaluation Stage	Peer-Review ▾
Evaluation Round	Round 3 ▾
Evaluation Date	20 Mar 2025
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Acceptance note

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 3 rounds of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review.

During triage, the handling editor identified no issues with the initial submission that were prohibitive of advancing to peer-review. The editor mainly suggested revisions for improving the clarity of presentation of the workflow.

During peer-review, the evaluators recommended that authors provide greater discussion of the rationale and context for the workflow being described, the addition of examples to illustrate parts of the workflow, and a thoughtful discussion about strengths and weaknesses of the workflow. These issues were addressed by the authors to the satisfaction of the editor and peer-reviewers.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12796100>